

Operational conditions to obtain high-value products from sewage sludge

Deliverable 6.4

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

This WP proposes a “start to end” valorisation process of the urban sewage sludge (USS) and organic fraction from municipal solid waste (OFMSW) to obtain ready-to-use products. Different processes will be studied to demonstrate the feasibility to obtain high-value products from raw biowastes (OFMSW and USS). These processes will be validated in prototypes operated in three demonstration sites: DS 1 (ES), DS6 (CZ) and DS7 (NL). Special attention will be given to the key operation parameters and system design for the production of target valuable end-products to be adapted at DSs.

The advanced anaerobic digestion pilot plant treats primary and secondary sludge (mixed sludge) produced in the Estiviel Sewage Treatment Plant (STP) located in DS1 (Spain) through a twostaged bioelectrochemical route (Dual Anaerobic Digestion). This process aims to obtain high quality biogas and biosolids with enhanced sanitation properties for land application.

At DS7 (The Netherlands), a pilot of the PHARIO technology is being developed for PHA (Polyhydroxyalkanoates) production from municipal surplus secondary activated sludge and fermented organic waste. PHA are biodegradable thermoplastics with the potential to replace fossil fuel based polymers.

The bioelectrochemical system (BES) target is to bioelectrochemically convert the CO₂ content of the biogas produced from the digestion of USS or OFMSW into valuable organic compounds. This prototype has been installed in DS 1 (Spain) treating biogas from OFMSW and will be further tested in DS 6 (Czech Republic) in future stages of the project, treating biogas from USS.

Deliverable 6.4 aims to describe the start-up stage of each process and the operational conditions that will be considered in order to achieve optimization. The operational conditions that will be tested to achieve optimization will not only consider the key parameter of end-products quality, but also energy and material consumption, operational and maintenance requirements, in order to get a whole life-cycle performance

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